

Examine the impact of advertising media on the consumer purchasing behavior of FMCG Products

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Abstract

The research paper study was conducted to screen out the examine the impact of advertising media on the consumer purchasing behavior of FMCG products. Advertising is a promotion strategy that serves as a major tool in creating product awareness in the mind of the consumer to take a purchasing decision. A questionnaire was created and circulated to capture the data from the consumers, and 108 responses were collected. Sample data were collected from all over India. After collecting responses from the questionnaire data, an expert interview was conducted. Based on the expert interview thematic analysis was done in which responses were collected and then manually coded in the form of themes. Major themes were sorted out from the common themes. Thematic analysis showed that there is a relationship between consumer and advertising media. There is an impact of social media among consumers, and they find a relationship between products and media. There is an impact factor when consumers choose to review before purchasing products. The results show significant factors affecting consumers from advertising media.

Objectives: To carefully examine anonymous customers' free-text remarks to find new trends and understand how advertising media affects consumers.

Design: Free-text data from a population-based survey that was thematically analysed.

Settings and participants: A total of 108 participants are currently working in different sectors including working professionals, non-working people, and students. Of which an expert interview was conducted.

Main outcome measures: Theme expressions in the free text are coded. Overarching topics are identified using comment categories.

Methods: Twenty-five respondents provided free-text replies. A multi-step process was used to code the data: general categories were created from the comments, after which subcategories within those categories were coded, themes that cut across categories were found using cross-sectional analysis, and finally categories and subcategories were mapped to corresponding closed questions.

Results: Most poll participants expressed optimism over the compatibility and influence of advertising media. We discovered some common themes via conducting interviews with folks. Some of these themes include brand awareness, mature audiences, social media review reliability, product relationships, and dynamic social media. These sections delve into the underlying subthemes.

Conclusion: This study analyses several traits that are present throughout the entire shopping experience and focuses on the influence of the advertising media on the consumer purchasing behavior of FMCG products. Even while most

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responses were positive, further research showed that a sizeable percentage of respondents were doubtful. Brand awareness can help to ease these worries, even in cases when social media review reliability is present.

Keywords: Mature audience; Product relation; Social media reliability; Dynamic social media; Brand awareness

1. Introduction

The size of the global FMCG market, which was estimated to be worth \$11,490.9 billion in 2021, is expected to grow to \$18,939.4 billion by 2031, a 5.1% CAGR from 2022 to 2031. In today’s competitive era, one is constantly bombarded with advertisements. (Ms. Anindita Kundu, Prof. Prashant Kulkarni, & Prof. Anantha Murthy N.K, 2008)

The largest category of consumer goods is known as fast-moving consumer goods (FMCG), also known as consumer-packaged goods (CPG). Food, drink, personal care, and home care products are among the durable and non-durable goods that are included. Advertising is a way of communication to encourage an audience for making a purchase decision about a product or service and conveying information to viewers. (Haider & Shadman Shakib, 2017). FMCG products are necessary for daily living. These products are widely consumed by members of every social class, who also spend a sizable percentage of their money on them. The FMCG product category contributes significantly to the economy. The items in the FMCG category have a rapid turnover. A vast variety of frequently bought consumer goods, both durable and non-durable, are available in the worldwide FMCG market. They include deodorants, soap, toiletries, cosmetics, tools for shaving and cleaning teeth, detergents, and non-durable consumer goods like glassware and other paper goods.

Global population growth is inversely correlated with rising consumer goods demand. This is one of the main elements influencing the growth of the global FMCG market. Also, the increased middle-class population's discretionary income, the frequency with which manufacturers introduce new products, the effectiveness of brand advertising, and the market's robust distribution system all contribute to the expansion. More income leads to more FMCG product purchases. (Dinesh T, Indranil C, & Indranil C, 2023)

Figure 1 Growth of FMCG Market

In 2021, the segment of food and beverage held the largest share with 84.8%. The growth of the population, multiculturalism, and disposable income are what are driving the food and beverage industry.

Every customer has a unique thought process and attitude when it comes to purchasing a product (Geetanjali Shrivastava, Vaishnavi Nagar, & Simranjeet Kaur Gill, 2021). Everything is available online in the twenty-first century, and customers are aware of the advantages of digitization. The consequences of advertising continue to accelerate every year. (Prof. Dr. Abdul Ghafoor Awan , Muhammad Ismail, Captain Fauzia Majeed , & Farisa Ghazal, 2016). The bulk of consumer purchases are made online or through e-commerce in large metropolitan areas, and this tendency is increasingly spreading to non-metropolitan areas as well. Due to the significant expansion in internet connection across metros and non-metros, mobile app shopping is becoming a popular trend in the FMCG industry. Consumers will

continue to gain influence over the next ten years through utilizing new communication technology. India added 260 million new internet users in 2015, and by 2025, it's anticipated that there will be 900 million internet users there.

Due to established markets like the U.S., China, and others, the FMCG market has increased tremendously. Almost 70% of the increase in consumer spending expected globally is anticipated to come from these. By 2030, India would have surpassed Japan and Germany to become the third-largest market in the world in terms of overall consumer spending, according to World Bank predictions.

1.1. FAQs

1.1.1. Q1. What will be the FMCG Market Size From 2021 to 2030?

With a projected CAGR of 5.1% from 2022 to 2031, the size of the global market for fast-moving consumer products, which was estimated to be worth \$11,490.9 billion in 2021, is expected to grow to \$18,939.4 billion by 2031. Increased consumer knowledge of FMCG items, rising middle-class disposable income, regular product launches by manufacturers, successful brand advertising, and a robust FMCG sector distribution network all contribute to the market's expansion. More income leads to more FMCG product purchases.

1.1.2. Q2. What is the CAGR of the FMCG Market?

From 2022 to 2031, the worldwide FMCG market is anticipated to grow at a CAGR of 5.1%. The market's expansion can be attributed to rising disposable income and increased e-commerce penetration in both established and emerging markets.

1.2. Overview of the Indian FMCG sector

The fourth-largest sector of the Indian economy is fast-moving consumer goods (FMCG). The sector is divided into three primary categories: food and beverage accounts for 19% of the sector; healthcare accounts for 31% of the share; and household and personal care make up the remaining 50%. About 55% of the revenue share comes from the urban segment, while 45% comes from the rural section. The FMCG market will be driven by a rise in rural consumption. According to projections, the Indian processed food market will grow from US\$ 263 billion in 2019–20 to US\$ 470 billion by 2025.

Notwithstanding widespread lockdowns, the Indian FMCG business increased by 16% in CY21, a 9-year high, thanks to consumption-driven growth and value expansion from higher product prices, notably for basics. Throughout the period from 2015 to 20, final consumer spending grew at a CAGR of 5.2%. Real household expenditure is anticipated to rise 9.1% YoY in 2021 after declining >9.3% in 2020 because of the pandemic's economic effects, according to Fitch Solutions. According to CRISIL Ratings, the FMCG sector's sales growth would double from 5-6% in FY21 to 10-12% in FY22. Growth is being fueled by volume expansion, a rebound in demand for discretionary goods, price hikes across product categories that will balance the effects of increased raw material costs, and volume growth.

By 2026, at a CAGR of 28.99%, it is predicted that the Indian online grocery market will generate more than Rs. 1,310.93 billion (US\$ 17.12 billion) in sales. Over the next five years, the gross merchandise value (GMV) of the online grocery market in India is anticipated to rise 18 times, reaching US\$ 37 billion by FY25.

In a report jointly produced by the industry group FICCI and the real estate consulting firm Anarock, it is predicted that the Indian e-commerce business will grow from US\$ 38 billion in 2021 to US\$ 120 billion by 2026.

1.3. Research Methodology

Being able to mix visual and aural communication makes television advertising one of the most successful techniques for getting a message over to a target audience. As a result, it serves as a vital tool for raising public awareness of various items. The customers choose the FMCG products they use from a variety of products after learning more about each one. The findings of a study conducted to determine the impact of advertising media on consumer purchasing behavior are presented in this project. A consumer consumes goods & services product. Marketing aims to meet and satisfy the target customer's needs & wants.

In contrast to earlier studies, which evaluated the effects of such communication processes on consumers in the context of household decision-making, the goal of this research paper is to investigate various factors that affected consumers' purchasing behavior, satisfaction with FMCG product advertising strategies, monthly spending, etc.

2. Material and methods

2.1. Research Objectives

To examine the impact of advertising media on the consumer purchasing behavior of FMCG Product

To examine modern consumer preferences.

2.2. Study Design

To determine how participants evaluated the impact of advertising media on the consumer purchasing behavior of FMCG products, this study used open-ended theme analysis. To gather data for the impact study, the researchers utilized a purposive sampling approach, in which they were given numerous sets of questions.

2.3. Questionnaire and design content

Questionnaires included sociodemographic, offline, and online product purchases, and more. Following the closed questions, a free-text survey was created and distributed to the people, asking: "Does extra personalization in advertisements annoy you?"

2.4. Survey process

Interviews with participants were conducted on a predefined and mutually agreed-upon day at their place of employment. The semi-structured interviews have a general framework for looking at the intriguing topics offered by the guide. Are social media and advertisement media influential? was the main query. When appropriate, the interviewer encouraged participants to go into further detail about interesting or important statements.

2.5. Participants

To maximize the use of a few resources, intentional sampling is a frequent technique in qualitative research that selects samples that are most likely to be information-rich on the topic of interest. Households, working adults, and students were among the respondents. Participants had to be at least 18 years old and either full-time workers or students enrolled in higher education. The researchers sent emails to prospective employees asking them to participate in interviews regarding their IT experience. No compensation was given to survey takers.

The objectives of this study involved interviewing 25 people. Since the goal of the study was to gain a thorough understanding of the point of interest (i.e., participants' experiences of making purchases while being influenced by advertisements), data like mean age, etc., are not reported because they may unjustifiably give the impression of generalizability and quantitative robustness.

2.6. Conceptual Background

The theoretical framework is presented in the early section of a dissertation and provides the rationale for conducting your research to investigate a particular research problem. Consider the theoretical framework as a conceptual model that establishes a sense of structure that guides your research. It provides the background that supports your investigation and offers the reader a justification for your study of a particular research problem. It includes the variables you intend to measure and the relationships you seek to understand. Essentially, this is where you develop a "theory" and build your case for investigating that theory. The theoretical framework is a summary of your theory regarding a particular problem that is developed through a review of previously tested knowledge of the variables involved. It identifies a plan for investigation and interpretation of the findings.

The theoretical framework involves a well-supported rationale and is organized in a manner that helps the reader understand and assess your perspective. The purpose is to demonstrate that the relationships you propose are not based on your instincts or guesses, but rather formed from facts obtained from authors of previous research.

The theoretical framework is how you conceptualize the nature of your research problem, its basis, and the analysis you will choose to investigate that problem. This framework determines how you perceive, make sense of, and interpret your data. An explanation of the theoretical framework helps the reader understand your perspective and context. There is a link between theoretical framework and quantitative research design.

2.7. Independent and Dependent variables

Figure 2 Dependent & Independent variables

Numerous independent factors that influence the dependent variable are frequently involved in causal linkages. I have, however, just used 3 independent variables to keep things straightforward i.e., print media, digital media, and social media.

I've utilized the fundamental design elements of boxes and arrows to represent the predicted cause-and-effect connection. Every variable has its box. Each line should originate from the independent variable (the cause) and point toward the dependent variable to denote a causal link (the effect).

- **Print Media:** Print media refers to all the different kinds of print media techniques including, Newspapers, brochures, banners, holdings, etc. It enables customers to get indulged in the advertisement and products specification.
- **Digital Media:** Digital media refers to all the different kinds of digital media forms including TV, website, blog, email, podcasts, etc. They provide the medium for advertisers to reach out to their targeted customers.
- **Social Media:** social media refers to all the different kinds of social media forms including social networking sites like Instagram, Facebook, YouTube Etc. They are the fastest mode for advertisement, and the reach of the advertisement is very versatile on social networking sites.

2.8. Data Analysis and Findings

The data was collected with the help of a Google form survey form. The aim was to collect the ground reality via a survey form. People gave their responses in the Google form and a total of 108 responses were collected.

The findings from Google are presented here:

People were from different age groups, but most of the age group was 21 -31.

Figure 3 Percentage of Age Group

Figure 4 Percentage of Purchase behaviour

*77.8% of people purchase according to their needs and only 22.2% of people purchase with the influence of advertisement.

Figure 5 Percentage of mode of Influential Media

*41.7% of people are influenced by social media, 39.8% of people are influenced by digital media and 18.5 % of people are influenced by print media.

Figure 6 Percentage of Influential Media

*75% of people believe that advertisement media is influential, and 25% of the population believe the opposite.

Figure 7 Percentage of personalization on advertisement

*75% of the population feel that extra personalization in an advertisement makes people annoyed and 25% of people feel the opposite.

Figure 8 Percentage of social media presence

*84.3% of people believe that having a social media presence is essential for a brand and 15.7 % people don't believe so.

Figure 9 Percentage of Social media handle for product review

*The major proportion is covered by as 38% of people trust YouTube for product reviews and 33.3 % people believe Instagram is a better option and 23.1 believe Facebook is more useful for product reviews.

2.9. Thematic analysis

Based on the responses collected from the survey the next step was to conduct an expert interview with industry people, professors, and students as well.

For that interview process, I organized an expert interview based on the responses collected from the survey form. I took the interview a total of 25 people from the industry level and teaching sector and students.

10 people were from Industry, 7 from the teaching sector, and 8 students. Due to repetitive responses, only 65 responses were recorded. Out of 25, five interviews were conducted over the phone while the remaining were in person. For easier understanding, the data was collected and organized in an Excel file.

2.10. Data analysis from the Expert interview

2.10.1. Stages of Research Findings

Figure 10 Stages of Research Findings

- **Stage 1:** The first stage is analyzing the semantic content of the entire free-text data set as well as whether comments were positive or negative. A coding taxonomy was developed to help categorize qualitative data.
- **Stage 2:** Individual categories went through the second round of more extensive categorization into Themes. For example, comments on Impacts were classified into the theme's advertisement media and then 'mature audience' or 'product relation' at stage 1. In the second step, codes were further decoded into Themes.
- **Stage 3:** Cross-sectional analysis was performed on codes/themes to highlight common themes found across different themes.

The word cloud represents the codes converted from the themes. These are the codes that were generated manually.

3.3. The process

The expert interviews were conducted with industry research analysts, teachers, and students. The whole interview was captured in audio form and then the audio transcription was done manually in an Excel sheet. After the audio transcription was then studied carefully and codes were assigned to every individual respondent. After code generation, the next step was to convert these codes into themes. The whole process was done manually.

4. Discussion

According to the findings of this research, advertisements have a significant impact on the buying behavior of consumers. The research is based on an examination of the impact of advertisement media on the consumer purchasing behavior of FMCG products. Marketers try to influence consumer behavior through various tools like quality, brand image, offers, discounts, and so on (Dholakiya & Dr. Vishal Doshi, 2022). Consumer behavior is the study of how individual customers, groups or organizations select, buy, use, and dispose of ideas, goods, and services to satisfy their needs and wants. It refers to the actions of the consumers in the marketplace and the underlying motives for those actions. Findings from this research are that 84.3% of the people believe that the presence of social media is important for a brand and 15.7% believe that social media presence is not important. Most consumers do not accept the claims made in commercials, but in this case, tastes and income levels are actively driving demand for the product even if it is known that the claims may not be accurate. The attractiveness of the product is another factor that influences the purchasing decision.

Advertisements should be created by the target audience's purchasing patterns and customs.

Today's consumers are greatly influenced by social media, which can be exploited skillfully for better outcomes. Advertisements should be realistic, and for more effect, celebrities like actors, athletes, or professionals might be used. Findings from the thematic analysis are that different codes and themes can be described for the impact of advertisement media. 5 common themes are derived from the data set of codes and themes.

The 5 common themes are *Mature audience, Product relation, dynamic social media, social media review reliability, and brand awareness*.

4.1.1. Mature Audience

More time is spent shopping by older customers. They prefer personal service from chatty, cheerful cashiers, as a result, not efficiency. They do not want to be quickly processed by checkout staff using laser scanners; they want to sit down and have a cup of coffee. Those who buy items when they need them are not by any kind of impact of advertising media, as shown by survey forms and expert interviews. Nowadays, people are becoming wiser consumers.

4.1.2. Product Relation

Customer relations are the strategies a business uses to interact with its clients and enhance the client experience. Most respondents who responded to the free text survey highlighted how crucial advertisements are to people's lives. People occasionally relate to commercials and find them relatable. The connection between advertisements and brands is crucial.

4.1.3. Dynamic social media

Fingers start swiping and it's difficult to stop them when there are thousands of advertisements and posts scattered throughout feeds. Video and dynamic material are crucial because of this. Nowadays, individuals regularly use social media because of its wide audience diversity, dynamic reach, and dynamic user base.

4.1.4. Social media review reliability

Potential clients might learn authentic information about your company differently on each social media site. On these platforms, there is no dependability. This makes social media unreliable in terms of social media reviews.

4.1.5. Brand Awareness

Consumers' familiarity with a specific good or service. Because social media sites like YouTube, Facebook, Instagram, and others help to develop brand recognition among consumers, advertisements play a crucial role in this process. Brand awareness is the term used to describe how familiar consumers are with a specific brand or service.

5. Conclusion

The current paper concluded that, the impact of advertisements on consumer purchases of FMCG products. In the present scenario, advertisements play a vital role in communicating with target customers through effective messages, and they can communicate with the final customer through the best visual and audio communication. The study also confirmed that most administrators are concerned with the influence of brand community management in creating business advantage. Consumers no longer must rely on traditional media to acquire information about a product before making their purchase since social media can effectively and easily avail of such information. For that reason, social media service providers must come up with effective measures for controlling publication timing, frequency, and content to achieve the set marketing targets. So, companies need to appreciate that proper management of online strategies and brand community in creating community identity enhances the brand's competitiveness and inspires members of the brand community to shun using goods and services from competitors.

Compliance with ethical standards

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Disclosure of conflict of interest

The authors of this research paper declare that there are no conflicts of interest to disclose. We affirm that we have no financial, professional, or personal relationships that could be perceived as potentially influencing the research findings, biases, or the objectivity of this study. This includes any affiliations, funding sources, consultancies, or stock ownership that could have influenced the design, conduct, or reporting of the research. We hereby confirm that the research and its outcomes were conducted with the utmost integrity, objectivity, and transparency.

We believe it is essential to provide this disclosure to maintain the highest standards of scientific integrity and to ensure transparency in the research process. By declaring the absence of conflicts of interest, we aim to uphold the credibility and trustworthiness of this study, allowing readers to evaluate the research with confidence.

Please note that this statement represents the author's declaration of the absence of conflicts of interest. If any conflicts of interest arise after the publication of this research paper, the authors commit to promptly disclosing such conflicts in an appropriate manner.

Statement of informed consent

The participants included in this study provided informed consent prior to their involvement. They were provided with a clear explanation of the purpose, procedures, and potential risks and benefits of participating in the research. The participants were assured that their participation was voluntary and that they had the right to withdraw from the study at any time without any repercussions. Confidentiality and anonymity were maintained throughout the research process, and the data collected were used solely for the purposes of this study. The participants were informed that their contribution would be greatly valued and would contribute to the advancement of knowledge in the respective field.

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Authors short Biography

Manish Pushkar, Research Analyst, I am a Research Analyst with a strong background in Marketing and Operations, holding an MBA degree. Alongside my role as a Research Analyst, I am actively engaged in content writing, specializing in the research industry. With a focus on consumer behavior, I have contributed to numerous research papers exploring various aspects of this field. Research is not only my profession but also my passion, as I believe it is an ongoing process that drives continuous learning and growth. Through my work, I strive to contribute valuable insights and make meaningful contributions to the world of research.

Appendix

Proof of Manual code analysis and theme generation

Common Themes					
	Q1	Q2	Q3	Q4	Q5
R1	Mature Audience	Positive personalization	Value of social media	Social media review	Dynamic reach
R2	Smart purchaser	Positive personalization	branded social media	Personal touch	Social media reach
R3	Ads influencers	Negative personalization	Importance of brand	Social media review reliability	Brand Awareness
R4	According to need	Misleading	Digitalization	Positive social media review	Brand awareness
R5	Need Purchaser	Product relation	Dynamic social media	Misslead review	Agree
R6	Importance of brand	Negative personalization	Digitalization	Personal touch	Social media reach
R7	Positive social media review	Dynamic social media	Dynamic social media	Personal touch	Brand Awareness
R8	Positive social media review	branded social media	branded social media	Misslead review	Brand Awareness
R9	branded social media	Social media review	Value of social media	Social media review reliability	Social media reach
R10	Positive personalization	According to need	Positive social media review	Social media review	Dynamic reach
R11	Dynamic reach	Positive personalization	Misslead review	Positive social media review	Social media reach
R12	Agree	Negative personalization	branded social media	Digitalization	Positive social media review
R13	Smart purchaser	Negative personalization	Value of social media	Positive social media review	Importance of brand
R14	influence of marketing	Personalization	Social media	Not reliable	Reliable
R15	Customer preference	Impacts on ads	larger customers	availability of advance tools	Social media

5 Common Themes	1) Mature Audience 2) Product relation 3) Dynamic social media 4) Social media review reliability 5) Brand Awareness
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Questionnaire form

Examine the impact of advertising media on the consumer purchasing behavior of FMCG Products

- Objectives
 - To study the impact of advertising media on consumer purchasing behavior on FMCG products.
 - To study the effect of demographic variables on consumer purchasing behavior on FMCG products.
- Section (A)
 - Full Name:
 - Email:
 - Mob no:
 - Age:
 - Occupation:
- Section (B)
 - What do you consider for purchasing products?
 - According to your needs
 - Influenced by advertisements.
 - Which mode is most influential for you?
 - Print media.
 - Digital media
 - Social media

- Are you likely to change your decision to purchase a product if it has gotten a bad review on social media?
 - Yes
 - No
- Do you think that Brand Ambassadors play a very vital role in advertisements?
 - Yes
 - No
- Are Advertisement media / social media advertisements influential?
 - Yes
 - No
- Do you consider them trustworthy?
 - Yes
 - No
- Do you view these advertisements?
 - Yes
 - No
- Does extra personalization in an advertisement make you feel annoyed?
 - Yes
 - No
- Do you think having a social media presence is essential for a brand?
 - Yes
 - No
- Which social media handle do you trust the most when it comes to product reviews?
 - Instagram
 - Facebook
 - YouTube
 - Pinterest
 - Others